

QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHODS IN EXPERIMENTAL TRAINING OF MONOLOGICAL REFLECTION-BASED SPEECHES

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Abstract. *Studies have shown that the use of reflexive skills increases the likelihood that students will gain a more effective professional approach and memory recall. The visual and auditory properties of the videos attract a wide audience and allow each user to process information uniquely. Reflective practice increases the potential of students to improve at least for the following reasons: to create the opportunity to learn from educational practice on an ongoing basis, as well as to study the flow of professional demands and suggestions.*

Keywords: *reflexivity, training, professional experience, research scope, innovative style.*

Consideration of research methodology is necessary start by defining the paradigm within which a given research will be carried out. As you know, a paradigm is “a certain system of scientific knowledge and patterns of activity accepted by the scientific community and determining the target orientation of scientific research” Today, in education, the dominant place is occupied by the anthropocentric paradigm, in which the center of the educational process is the student’s all its subjective characteristics. In connection with the transition to this paradigm, there have been changes in the conceptual foundations of methodology as a science. At present, system-activity, competence-based, intercultural, cognitive-communicative, personality-oriented, personality-activity approaches form the conceptual basis of modern research on the theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages. The educational process is focused not just on the “assignment” of a set of knowledge, skills and abilities by students, but on changing the motives and attitudes of the student. In connection with these changes, the goal of modern education is the formation of competencies, in the center of which lies the readiness and ability of the student to carry out a certain activity, which is based on knowledge, skills, abilities and his attitude towards it (activity). At the same time, a distinctive feature of the anthropocentric paradigm is the dominance of the last component (relationships) over all the others (knowledge, skills and abilities). In addition to changing the basic concepts, changing the educational paradigm also entails, based on the system-structural approach developed by I.L. Beam, and a change in the methodological apparatus, in particular, the nomenclature of research methods.

In domestic science, quantitative (statistical) research methods are widely used, with the help of

which it is possible to assess the growth of knowledge and shifts in the field of skills of students. However, with their help it is impossible to reveal the attitudes of students to activities. The anthropocentric paradigm involves expanding the scope of using qualitative research methods aimed at ascertaining the changes that occur both in terms of skills and attitudes, personal qualities, motives, and values of students. The use of qualitative research methods has become widespread abroad, and is also beginning to attract the interest of domestic researchers, as evidenced by a number of scientific publications.

Unlike quantitative research methods, that answer the questions "How often?" and “How much?”, Qualitative research methods provide an answer to the questions: “What?”, “How?” and

“Why?”, thus allowing you to penetrate deep into the problems under study (in-depth research) and obtain reliable data that provide a comprehensive explanation of the issues under study. A similar depth of qualitative research is also achieved by the joint work of the researcher and the subjects, during which the researcher receives first-hand data, which contributes to a true understanding of the problem.

In addition, the use of qualitative research methods makes it possible to implement an individual approach to students, since they (methods) interpret the results of the experiment not from the point of view of the researcher, but from the point of view of the subject of the study (from the perspective of the subject, not the researcher)

While statistical methods give the researcher average indicators, as a result of which work with the specific personality of the student, his personality and the context of educational activity is out of the researcher's field of vision [Sorokina 2011].

At the same time, qualitative research methods are devoid of shortcomings, the main of which is the impossibility of their application to a large number of subjects.

In this regard, the undoubted advantage of quantitative methods is their reliability, which is achieved by covering a larger number of respondents, which ensures the objectivity of the results obtained. But as scientists point out, the validity of qualitative methods is higher than quantitative ones. This due to the fact that when using quantitative methods, the study is under strict control, which can lead to artificiality of the situation, while qualitative methods explore the ongoing shifts in the activity and motivational-value aspects in the usual for student conditions. Qualitative research methods include: the study of the phenomenon (phenomenology), the method of cases (case study), grounded theory, ethnography (ethnography), qualitative discourse analysis (discourse analysis), semi-structured and unstructured interviews, work with focus groups and participant observation (observation). The hypothesis of our study is the fact that teaching monologue speech based on reflection contributes both to the development of speech skills (to independently produce discourses) and to the development of reflection, which must subsequently become an inalienable property of the individual. Based on the creative nature of reflexive processes, one can conclude that the very dynamics of the development of reflection can hardly be studied and evaluated using quantitative methods. In addition, the very process of generating different types of discourse (descriptive, narrative, argumentative) with linguistic features characteristic of each of them (starting from structure and ending with connectors) requires the use of not only statistical, but also qualitative research methods (questionnaires, discourse analysis, interviews, focus groups, participant observation).

On the example of the technology of teaching descriptive discourse, let's consider the research methods used. In order to determine the level of reflection proficiency, a survey, which showed that some students have ideas about reflexive processes, while others do not have such ideas. In this regard, we turned to the methods of conversation and research of the phenomenon. The method of conversation contributed to the formation (and in some cases, improvement) of knowledge about reflection and its significance, and the method of studying the phenomenon was aimed at internalizing the knowledge gained. Under the study of the phenomenon, B. Hancock understands the method description of something that exists as part of its environment us world (events, situations, experiences, concepts) [Hancock 1998: p. 4]. At the same time, the author notes that the study of a phenomenon begins when a person recognizes that there is a gap

in his understanding of something that needs to be filled. With regard to our experiential learning, the method of studying the phenomenon is as follows. A student may know what reflection is (has an idea about it), but does not know how and when to use reflection, how to start reflecting, what a person experiences when he reflects, etc. In the process of studying reflexive processes, their comprehension and practical application, the student receives information, masters the skills of reflection, forms his own attitude towards it, which he then describes in interview at the end of the experiential training.

In parallel with the method of studying reflection, the case study method was used, which we understand as “a research method aimed at studying a specific situation, a particular case that exists in reality”. Scientists agree that the number of objects of study of this method can be extremely limited (one or two), but when using the case method, the scientist receives rich and detailed information about the object of study (it offers a richness and depth of information), which is usually missing when using other methods.

In our study, the subjects of the case method are three students who differ in the level of proficiency in monological speech: one student has a high level, the second has an average level, and the third student has a low level. Over the course of two months of work on a descriptive discourse based on reflection, we trace how the reflective and speech skills of these students change. We believe that such a selection of subjects is justified by the fact that the results of the study will give us the opportunity to understand the patterns of development of monologue speech based on reflection in students with a high, medium and low level of development of speech skills.

In the process of applying the case method, we used methods for collecting qualitative data, the essence of which disclosed below.

Focus group work is an interview, only conducted not with one respondent, but with a group. The main condition for applying this method of collecting information is to provide greater understanding and better analysis of the issue in group interaction than in individual [Hancock 1998: 10]. In our study, work with a focus group was carried out in the form of a retrospective analysis of monologue statements by students (discourses-sample and discourses of classmates). The work with the focus group preceded the interview, because in the process of joint answering questions and joint discussion, students understood the essence of reflection more deeply, ceased to feel embarrassment, fears (which inevitably arose due to the novelty of the activity), in addition, they pronounce in a loud speech those steps that they had to carry out on their own during subsequent individual work, thereby bringing the skill to automatism.

Unstructured (free), as well as semi-structured interviews, consist of open (open-ended) questions, with the difference that during unstructured interviews, the researcher usually only knows how to start it, and after the first question, his tactics depends entirely on the answers of the respondent. At the same time, the goal of the researcher is to discuss in detail the minimum number of questions (often one). In semi-structured interviews, the researcher controls the course of the conversation and can ask leading questions to the respondent, which allows the interlocutors to discuss in detail several of the researcher's interesting questions. So, in our study, as part of the application of the case method, we conducted semi-structured interviews, which contributed to students' understanding of the role of reflection in the process of generating a monologue statement. Sample semi-structured interview questions: Is reflection useful for you to understand and evaluate the quality of your oral statement / to get an idea of how you can

improve the quality of your statement / to help you identify and systematize errors in your speech / to understand your strengths and weaknesses in speaking in English / to plan your individual work on the development of speaking skills? How often do you reflect in the process of speaking (after speaking, before speaking? At the end of the experiential training, we conducted free (unstructured) interviews with students who were subjects of the case method. We began the unstructured interview with the question: I would like to hear your opinion on the role of reflection in the process of generating a monologue statement.

Participatory observation allows the researcher to judge the correspondence of respondents' answers to interviews with their real behavior, thereby bringing objectivity to the study. In our case, we observed how students reflect and how they take into account the conclusions obtained as a result of reflection in the process of monologue statements, correlating the results of observation with the data obtained as a result of the interview. Along with the included observation, we also used the method of qualitative discourse analysis (from the point of view of reflexive processes), in which the transcripts of students' monologue statements were studied. As a result of the analysis of the discourse, the researcher drew conclusions, then compared them with the conclusions that the student (the author of the discourse) came to, thereby studying both the dynamics of the development of reflexive actions in the process of experiential learning and the existing shortcomings in order to purposefully manage the process of forming reflection.

In parallel with qualitative research methods quantitative methods were also used, in particular: discourse analysis in terms of the linguistic means used (connectors, construction structures, etc.), questioning, survey, statistical data analysis.

Processing of the first results of the experimental teaching descriptive discourse confirmed our hypothesis on the effectiveness of the integrated use of quantitative and qualitative methods with the leading role of qualitative methods in the study of reflection. This made it possible to multilaterally explore the variable element of the developed technology, in our case, the process of the formation of reflection and its influence on the mastery of oral descriptive discourse.

REFERENCES

1. Charoenruk D. Communication Research Methodologies: Qualitative and Quantitative Methodology / D. Charoenruk. – 2007. – URL: http://utcc2.utcc.ac.th/localuser/amsar/PDF/Documents49/quantitative_and_qualitative_methodologies.pdf (дата обращения 01.12.2012).
2. Cormack D.S. The Research Process.– Oxford: Black Scientific. – 1991. – 549 p.
3. Duffy M.E. Methodological triangulation a vehicle for merging quantitative and qualitative methods // Image : Journal of Nursing Scholarship. – 1987. – Vol. 19. – № 3. – P. 130–133.
4. Hancock B. An Introduction to Qualitative Research / B. Hancock. – Nottingham: Trent Focus, 1998. – URL: <http://classes.uleth.ca/200502/mgt2700a/Articles/Qualitative%20Research.pdf> , свободный.
5. Semenov I.N. Reflexive pedagogy and psychology of creative thinking. Zaporozhye, ZSU, 1992.
6. Soliev E. English for Mechanical Engineering/ Toshkent.: 2022.

7. Vasyutin R.N. Reflexive method in continuing education // Proceedings of the IV European Congress of Psychologists. Athens, 1995.
8. Гальскова Н.Д. Основные парадигмальные черты современной методической науки / Н.Д. Гальскова // Иностранные языки в школе. – 2011. – № 7. – С. 2–11.
9. Сорокина Н.В. Кейс-стади как метод педагогического исследования / Н.В. Сорокина // Известия Волгоградского государственного педагогического университета. Серия «Педагогические науки». – 2011. – № 6. – С. 7–11.
10. Ibragimov, X., & Sh, A. (2008). *Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)*. T.: *Fan va texnologiya*, 288.
11. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). Креативность как одна из характеристик личности будущего педагога. *Наука, образование и культура*, (3 (27)), 44-46.
12. Хонимкулова, М. Х. К., & Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). Необходимость изучения иностранных языков: теория и практика. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (27 (39)), 80-83.
13. Ibragimovich, I. K. (2020). Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system. *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education*, 1, 6-15.
14. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2019). Теоретические аспекты социально-психологической адаптации студентов-первокурсников к обучению в вузе. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (26 (75)), 12-16.
15. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). Коммуникативная компетентность как механизм профессионального саморазвития будущего педагога. *Проблемы педагогики*, (2 (34)), 7-10.
16. Ibragimov, X., & Abdullaeva, S. H. (2008). Theory of pedagogy. *Science and Technology*.
17. Ибрагимов, Х. И. (2020). Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (7 (54)), 74-75.
18. Ibragimovich, X. I. (2021). O 'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA KREDIT-MODUL TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO 'LLASHNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 209-214.
19. Ibragimov, X. I., Yo'ldoshev, U. A., & Bobomirzayev, X. (2009). "Pedagogik Psixologiya" O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent.
20. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2019). Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых. *Academy*, (10 (49)), 39-41.
21. Атауллаев, Ф. Ф. У., & Ибраимов, Х. И. (2019). Понятие профессионально-коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей в психолого-педагогических исследованиях. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (1 (42)), 70-74.
22. Ibragimovich, I. K. (2018). Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (27 (39)), 78-80.
23. Ibragimovich, I. K., Kholboevna, I. F., Amrilloevich, I. A., & Rakhmonovich, U. S. (2021). PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT. *湖南大学学报 (自然科学版)*, 48(12).
24. Ибрагимов, Х. И. (2021). ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1 (80)), 608-611.

25. Ibragimov, X. I., & Salimova, Z. K. (2021). Relevance of english language science and teaching structure. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(4), 883-887.
26. Ibragimov, X. I., & Salimova, Z. K. (2021). Intensive in teaching english characteristics of application of methods. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1588-1594.
27. Rahmanovich, O. A., Yusufovich, E. H., Dilshodqizi, S. S., Almasovna, S. A., & Ibragimovich, H. I. (2020). Linguistic features of compound words in english and Uzbek languages. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(2), 925-932.
28. Bahtiyorova, F. H. USING FOLK LITERATURE IN THE PRIMARY ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS.
29. Ибраимов, X. И. (2018). НЕЙРОПЕДАГОГИКА КАК НОВОЕ ПРИКЛАДНОЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY* (pp. 6-10).
30. Ibragimovich, I. H., & Ghazzali, I. Increasing the Classical Activity of Future Teachers as a Pedagogical and Psychological Problem. *JournalNX*, 98-102.